

USE OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATION TOOLS IN TEACHING ORGANIC CHEMISTRY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Murodova Sitorabonu Bahodir kizi

Lecturer, Department of Chemistry, Bukhara State Pedagogical
Institute

e-mail: murodovasitorabonu98@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19436098>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 22nd March 2026

Accepted: 26th March 2026

Online: 31st March 2026

KEYWORDS

The proposed e-book "Organic Chemistry" was created in the programming language "Delphi" and "ActionScript". Parts of the e-textbook include

Today, special attention is paid to the supply of quality personnel in educational institutions for the development of our country and the modernization of the educational process. In accordance with the tasks defined in the "Strategy of Development" of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis and the People of Uzbekistan, the task of further raising the standard of living of the population, aligning the quality of education with advanced international standards, achieving sustainable economic growth and bringing our reforms to a new level to reduce poverty [1-2]

The proposed e-book "Organic Chemistry" was created in the programming language "Delphi" and "ActionScript". Parts of the e-textbook include:

Instructions for using the e-textbook are given in the login window

The program works with "Adobe Reader", "Adobe Flash Player", "Quick Time Player", "Media Player Classic" programs. When entering the program, it is entered through the serial number, and each user's first name and last name are entered. When the last name of the user is written, a folder with a special user name is created under this name on the "C" drive of the computer. The result received by this user will appear in this folder. When entering the program, the following screen will appear.

From the top, the first part is the lecture, the second part is the presentation, the third part is the experiment, the fourth part is the test, the fifth part is the glossary, the sixth part is the literature used in the creation of the program, and the last part is information about the authors of the program.

The lecture section provides sufficient information for each topic, as well as additional information. A database has been created to provide a complete overview of every topic in organic chemistry for the student. At the end of the lecture texts, questions on the topic are given. The student can strengthen the topic by finding answers to these questions.

After reading the lecture, the test questions prepared for this topic are solved and the test result is saved on the computer.

In order to increase competence, a question is asked on each topic, the answer of which is also stored on the computer.

In the second part, presentations were prepared on each topic. It is advisable for the reader to use the presentation to get more concise information and to conclude the topic for himself.

A general test is given in the test section. After mastering all topics, the student solves a test consisting of 25 prepared on these topics and is evaluated.

In the glossary part, there are chemical terms used in these topics and comments are given.

A list of used literature, as well as a link to the Bukhdu e-library is provided in the literature section.

The book of organic chemistry is also placed in 3D form in the literature section. It is possible to read and use the book. Additional programs that work with the program are also given [3-4].

Harmonious use of information technology and e-learning in organic chemistry classes in higher education institutions enabled students to activate their cognitive activities, acquire knowledge, skills and abilities according to their needs and interests, and self-control, and this was observed in increasing the effectiveness of independent education. The methods of organizing pedagogical experiments were used to determine and evaluate the effectiveness of the electronic textbook "Organic Chemistry" numbered DGU 22397. It has been proven that the use of electronic educational tools and modern educational technologies in teaching the subject of "Organic Chemistry" in higher educational institutions increases the effectiveness of education.

Used literature:

1. Flipped pedagogy: Strategies and technologies in chemistry education S. Athavan Alias Anand L. 322-332 p.
2. Abdukadirov A.A. Innovative technologies in education. - Tashkent: Talent, 2008. - 180 p.

3. Murodova S.B., Rahmonova R.R. Use of interactive methods in teaching organic chemistry// "PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT" scientific-theoretical and methodical magazine. – 2025. – T. - No. 1. – B. 16-19.
4. Murodova S.B. Use of virtual laboratory in teaching chemistry//Preschool and school education. – 2025. – T. – No. 12. - pp. 1596-1598.

